

ENHANCING FACULTY PERFORMANCE WITH FACULTY COMPENSATION – A MODEL BASED ON THEORY OF ACCOUNTABILITY (THEORY A)

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Abstract:

The objective of campus based higher education is now shifting from mass education to customized education and in such model involving students in research by faculty members is an essential part. Such research focused higher education model not only benefits the students but also provides an opportunity to the institution to create intellectual property in its name. To encourage faculty members to be involved in research and publications, HEIs are trying to find various strategies. Faculty compensation is one of the important strategies in higher education institutions as they are the brain of the system and creators of an intellectual asset to the institution. Making faculty compensation dynamic is a very attractive and effective way in order to involve faculty members in research and publications. In this paper, we have studied the changing objectives of autonomous HEIs towards developing Intellectual property by shifting their focus towards research and publication. As a part of such objectives, we have developed and discussed an improved model of faculty compensation based on Annual Performance Based Component (APBC) and discussed how it adds value to the HEIs to create a tangible asset of intangible intellectual property.

Keywords : HEI, Faculty performance, Dynamic Faculty compensation, Theory of Accountability, Factors affecting faculty performance.

1. INTRODUCTION :

Higher Education Institutions (HEI) are the part of the education industry which is a part of the tertiary sector service industry in the society. With the objective of providing quality service to the

students, industries, and society, HEIs are claiming autonomy to improve the quality through independent decisions at the institution level. In this regard, private universities in the world over have higher autonomy including making their financial decisions compared to public universities and other affiliated institutions (private or public) [1]. The quality aspect in HEI service is defined, delivered, and received by various stakeholders of the HEI system. In HEI system, the primary (internal) stakeholders are students, teachers, and management. Other (external) stakeholders are industry, alumni, government, and other accreditation institutions. The responsibilities of HEIs towards students, industries, and society are different and accordingly, they decide their objectives and set their targets to realize the objectives.

Table 1 : Objectives of autonomous HEI towards stakeholders

S. No.	Stakeholders	Objectives
1	Students	Imparting knowledge, skills, experience, ethics, and hence confidence to make them <i>innovative independent thinkers</i> .
2	Industries	Providing innovative graduates who can contribute effectively and efficiently for organizational productivity/ performance by transforming them <i>innovative independent thinkers & team players</i> .
3	Society	New knowledge, New interpretation of existing knowledge, by means creating, managing, and utilizing researching abilities of the intellectuals to create <i>intellectual property</i> .

Quality of higher education is considered as a service due to the reason that it is produced as a result of human labour and is intangible quantity developed as per the needs of the market. The quality in higher education depends on the organizational culture and tradition which further depends on four determinant factors including the quality of human resources (faculty & administrators), the way of managing the system, useful education programmes & methods, and the infrastructure which include buildings, facilities, and equipment. These performance or level quality determinant factors should meet the requirements of potential beneficiaries (students, industries, and society) [2]. The importance of these four quality determinant factors are further discussed below :

- (1) Quality of Human Resources : Quality of human resources include the quality of teaching, training, and the capability of creating new knowledge through and innovation by the faculty and students of the institution. Student involvement in research provides a new model of education called customised education which an effective strategy against the competition of distance education & MOOC based degree programmes.
- (2) Quality of Administrative & Managing system : The decisions taken by the administrative executives on creating, developing, maintain and further investment strategies and their vision, mission, and objectives both for the long term and short term in the higher education system are important to sustain the quality as well as to create a brand to the organization.
- (3) Quality of useful education programmes & methods : Right courses and right pedagogy are essential to attract and educate students in the higher education system. Offering industry oriented and

industry integrated courses and designing & implementing effective education and evaluation methodologies are supports quality in higher education.

(4) Quality of Infrastructure : Infrastructure is a very important determinant factor in attracting students to the HEI. Infrastructure includes land, buildings, and facilities like modern classrooms, modern library, sports & games, residential facilities both for students and faculties, state-of-art laboratories & workshops, auditorium, etc. for an ultra modern campus. But usually, high quality infrastructure increases the cost of education and hence student fee. Infrastructure gives an added advantage to the higher education system when other three quality determinant factors are appropriate.

Based on the above analysis, we can reframe the internal quality framework of higher education in a broad way as shown in figure 1.

Fig. 1 : Internal Quality framework of Higher Education System

Based on quality framework approach of HEI system, it can be argued that the Intellectual Property (IP1) of HEI which decides the quality of human resource, administrative setup, and programmes and methods, and Infrastructural Property (IP2) two major determinant issues which describe the quality and performance of HEI's.

Human resource/capital is the most critical asset in HEIs and using human resource/capital effectively to contribute and build the intellectual property of the organization is most important challenge and tactic for HEIs administrators.

2. IMPORTANCE OF IP(1) & IP(2) IN HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS :

Identifying and appointing suitable faculty members who have inherent interest and capabilities to participate in research and contribute for new knowledge creation both individually and through team work and skill of publishing them in journals and books or patenting them in institutional name to generate intellectual property should be given priority in HEIs. Creating new knowledge and converting it into IP-1 is important to higher education institutions for their accelerated growth and competitive advantage. Intellectual property of a HEI comprising of published journal papers, Conference papers, edited books, published books, published edited chapters, filed patents, copyrights, trademarks, designed rights, and Thesis books of masters, Ph.D., and post doctoral degrees are very important accumulated intellectual property which may give earning opportunity, branding opportunity, public value creation, and international recognitions.

Fig. 2 : Block diagram representing HEIs assets as Intellectual Property and its benefits.

It is observed that earlier, private universities have given less importance to research than offering new attractive courses along with attractive infrastructure. As a result, a larger share of research contribution is registered from public universities. As time progress, private universities realized that only infrastructure and new courses cannot differentiate them and give competitive advantage in higher education service offerings due to the fact that infrastructure and new course offerings can be provided at any time by other rivalry institutions and any new entrants to this business. Such universities which give importance to long time differentiation through research can only compete and sustain in a longer period. By realizing this truth of “Focusing on research & publication for enhanced sustainability” higher education institutions are changing their strategy and focusing on research and publications. In the process of such shifted focus from infrastructure to research and publication, HEIs are now changing their objectives, promoting research based curriculum and encouraging their faculty members and students to involve in research and publications. The advantages of research focus by autonomous HEIs by setting up a supportive environment is of many folds :

(1) Focus on research in teaching & training differentiates the campus based higher education model from a massive open online course (MOOC) model which is an information communication technology version of the distance education model.

- (2) Faculty members and students become active members of the system contributing to the new knowledge.
- (3) Higher education system becomes the dynamic contributing intellectual property of the HEIs so that as time progress, the intellectual asset of the institution/university grows in terms of both quantity and quality.
- (4) Based on the research focus of the institution, the faculty members get enhanced support and motivation in order to convert their ideas and new concepts into new knowledge or new interpretation leading to a systematic documentation of such new invention or innovation in published format.
- (5) Focus on scientific research in classrooms by involving students helps them to develop critical reasoning skills which are helpful to develop confidence for innovative thinking and crystallizing ideas in future days throughout their life.
- (6) Publishing the research findings and analysis in the national or international forum helps both faculty members and students to improve their systematic analysing ability, along with oral and written communication skills. This will automatically improve the quality of teaching and learning processes of both faculty members and students in the classrooms respectively.

Based on above facts, many autonomous universities especially private universities under higher education institutions have changed their objectives and converted themselves as research intensive universities. They have identified and developed suitable strategies to increase their research productivity by including both faculty members and students in developing and implementing research based curriculum [3-5]. Research intensive university primarily meets three criterions : (1) Focus on new knowledge creation, (2) Inherent spirit on critical inquiry, (3) Selecting faculty and students who have research interest. Many universities developed countries meet these criterions and branded as successful research universities. For example, the list of top 10 universities of 2018 in the USA as per www.Timeshighereducation.com and www.topuniversities.com are listed in Table 2 and it can be seen that all of them are research focussed private universities.

Table 2 : Top ten ranked universities in the USA

S. No.	Top Ranked Universities	Rank	Type	Focus
1	Stanford University	First (15K)	Private	Research focus
2	Massachusetts Institute of Technology (MIT)	Second (11K)	Private	Research focus
3	California Institute of Technology (CalTech)	Third (2K)	Private	Research focus
4	Harvard University	Fourth (20K)	Private	Research focus

5	Princeton University	Fifth (8,000)	Private	Research focus
6	University of Chicago	Sixth	Private	Research focus
7	Cornell University	Seventh	Private	Research focus
8	Yale University	Eighth	Private	Research focus
9	John Hopkins University / University of Pennsylvania	Ninth	Private	Research focus
10	Columbia University, Newyork	Tenth	Private	Research focus

3. FACULTY COMPENSATION IN HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS :

Various models of compensation for employees are used in the history in both production and service industries. This includes Pay for performance (P4P) model, Performance based bonus, Stock based compensation, Earning based compensation. Equality based compensation etc.

(1) Pay for performance (P4P) model : Pay for performance refers to a pay strategy where evaluations of individual and/or organizational performance have a significant influence on the amount of pay increase or bonus given to each employee.

(2) Performance based bonus : It is a type of additional compensation to be paid to an employee or group of employees as a reward for completing a particular task.

(3) Stock based compensation : This type of compensation involves the distribution of company stock to reward the performance of employees.

(4) Earning based compensation : This type of compensation in its simple terms involves the earnings of shares of the company during a given year and accordingly the compensation of executives is offered.

(5) Equality based compensation : In this type of compensation, the earnings of the employees are the same in a given grade/designation irrespective of their performance. Many organizations in the public sector and few of private sector organizations follow this model.

(6) Equity based compensation : It is a non-cash payment that represents ownership in the company. It may take different forms like options, restricted stock, and performance shares.

Productivity based compensation and Performance based compensation are two general types of meaningful compensation for production industries and service industries respectively. In the case of Higher Education Institutions industry, usually, the faculty compensation is defined by their responsibilities in a specified designation which consists of teaching, research, administrative and/or clinical. The total compensation is sum of various

components which may include (1) fixed component based on their designation and years of service in that designation, (2) fixed allowances based on fixed component, and (3) variable component based on annual academic performance indicator score and is called as Annual performance based component (APBC). This variable component is a very important part in every pay structure and essential to differentiate the employee contribution in organizational development.

In this paper, we have developed and discussed an improved model of faculty compensation based on Annual Performance Based Component (APBC) and discussed how it adds value to the HEIs to create a tangible asset of intangible intellectual property. Annual Performance Based Component is nothing but the contribution of a faculty to research and publication leading to the contribution to intellectual property (IP-1) asset of the HEI.

4. THEORY OF ACCOUNTABILITY IN HEI :

Organization and hence faculty members accountability towards their students, industry, and society are now getting importance and becoming increasingly significant in Higher Education system over the past decades due to the reasons of increased competitions without expected quality, rising of HEI institutions costs, disappointing un-employability rate of graduates, employer concerns on inadequate knowledge and skills expected in the workplace, and comments on the learning and value that higher education system provides to the students.

Faculty accountability in higher education system became important in many countries during the last few decades of 20th century and many faculty performance indicators were developed to improve productivity and for institutional effectiveness. By the end of 20th century, many accountability reporting systems were mandated in many countries through their higher education accreditation boards. During the beginning of 21st century, much importance and encouragement are given to the institutional autonomy both in public and private sectors to re-define quality through organizational and faculty autonomy. This move encouraged many private universities to accelerate their quality improvement strategy due to the reason that they have financial as well as quick decision making freedom on various determinant factors of quality improvement in higher education. This autonomy resulted in speeding up the process of faculty accountability and encouragement to improve the quality, as well as a contribution to the society through their enhanced focus on creating more and more intellectual property in a time-phased manner. The quest for creating intellectual property by higher educational & research institutions is now given importance to faculty accountability in intellectual property creation along with teaching and training. Every faculty in higher education institution has the responsibility of involving in teaching & training as well as in research & publications. Research is an integrated component in the higher education system at the undergraduate level and postgraduate level by involving students in such activities. Autonomous HEIs have potential opportunity to introduce project based, case analysis, or patent analysis as qualitative research for undergraduate courses in association with faculty members as guides. Similarly, postgraduate students

can be involved in projects related to conceptual designs, explorative studies, data analysis, decision analysis, simulation, and empirical studies under the guidance of faculty members. These innovations in undergraduate and postgraduate curriculum open doors for student–faculty collaborative research and publications. Each such scholarly publication in the form of journal paper, conference paper, patent, chapters in edited books, or complete edited book published in the name of the institution is considered as the intellectual property of HEI and such accumulated intellectual property is the intangible but convertible asset of that institution. Creation, accumulation, and branding of such asset is the opportunity for faculty members of autonomous HEIs and challenge for administrators. Based on the idea of converting this intellectual property into an organizational asset for brand building and institutional performance indicator in the international scenario, HEIs have tremendous interest in encashing this opportunity. Creating and maintaining such intellectual property is a challenge for HEIs and if not planned and managed properly, they will lose a great chance of creating this priceless intangible asset for the organization using existing faculty members and students without any additional substantial investment. We strongly urge that the autonomous HEIs especially private universities have to really and seriously think on these lines and focus their attention in creating intellectual property (IP-1) as a precious asset and to accumulate it every year. Even though research and publication is an integral part of the duty of every faculty member in higher education, making them responsible in contributing to it is a serious challenge to the administrators. This can be addressed using recently developed organizational performance theory called Theory of Accountability (Theory A). Theory A identifies the various factors which affect the organizational human resources performance. The emphasis is on inspiration and accountability of employees. This theory is developed during 2016 by P. S. Aithal and P. M. Suresh Kumar [6]. The postulates of Theory A overrides the existing propositions of various theories of organizational human behaviour and motivation by adding a new and extended set of propositions to improve the productivity based on human performance. By controlling employees mindset and quest for creativity in a systematic way, propels the employees to contribute to the objectives of the organization. Using Theory A, any organization in every industry sector can develop their strategy to boost their output by enhancing operational efficiency. Implementation of the propositions of theory A enables organizations to accelerate the contribution of their employees by connecting the targets with responsibility and commitment which is further stimulated by comparing with role models and setting accountability. The essential ingredients of Theory A [6-13] are (1) Planning the task based on objectives, (2) Target setting for every employee, (3) Motivation for achievement, (4) Developing Work Strategies, (5) Commitment through Responsibility, (6) Role model for comparison, (7) Continuous follow-up through Monitoring & Guiding, and (8) Accountability as positive or negative encouragement.

The postulates of theory A connect the following factors of organizational performance [6] :

(1) Planning : As per Theory A, the vision, mission, and objectives of an organization should be clear on the organizational contribution towards development. Planning is the first determinant component of the theory A and finds a prominent role in transforming an organization by an optimized contribution from its employees. Theory A promotes employee planning in order to improve their contribution by understanding the organizational objectives. By jointly setting the objectives of the organization, an organization can encourage its employees to think and contribute innovatively. Theory A also suggests that the organization can develop its planning strategy as the blue ocean to

become a monopoly in its business. The planning component of theory A also supports the involvement of employees in analysing the institutional strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and challenges, either individually or jointly in order to transform the organization into a highly productive organization [7].

(2) Target setting : Target setting is the second determinant component of Theory A and is include setting the time bound target of individual and group of employees of the organization. Target can be set for the entire number of employees individually as activity target or jointly as output target. Time bound targets can be fixed for quarterly, half yearly, or annually based on institutional policy and should be communicated in time to every employee in the organization. Such a simulative environment creates challenges for the employees and makes them to redefine their individual and group goal. The strategy of target setting for individuals and groups in an organization according to theory A makes everybody to prepare and devote their effort towards better performance [8].

(3) Motivation : Motivation in Theory A is the third component and is helpful to the employees to discover their own potential through self-exploration. As per theory A, once the target for the optimum performance by the employees is set, the authorities of the organization should develop and implement policies to help the employees to meet the targets. Theory A identifies various motivational factors which support to identify weaknesses of employees, encouragement to perform at par with others, appreciation of individual contribution and performance, encouragement for collaborative works, developing task-based strategies for better performers etc [9].

(4) Work Strategies : Work strategy being the fourth component of Theory A is important for success. Work strategy promotes a time-frame plan for individuals and groups to fulfil their target. Thus, Theory A proposes teamwork through collaborative efforts with other people simultaneously as a multitasking model. Re-defining the target based on its successive fulfilment is another enabling part of the work strategies [10].

(5) Responsibility : This is the major component of Theory A and contributes to both individual and organizational success. When the employees show their responsibility towards contributing towards the organizational objective, the productivity of the organization will enhance. It is argued that based on personality type, only a few people can take responsibility by themselves for organizational contribution. External stimulus is required for others to point out their responsibilities. Other components of Theory A like target setting, motivation, encouragement, continuous follow-up, or showcasing a role model in internal or external to the organization is also to stimulate the responsibility among the employees [11].

(6) Role model : Employees in every organization should realize that a given challenge through target setting is possible to achieve. Only achievable objectives should be set while target setting stage. By showcasing the role models either internal or external to the organization in a similar field, any organization can build confidence among the employees and prove that the set targets can be achievable. A role model can be any employee in the organization who outperform and contribute highest to the organization. Irrespective of age, gender, position and any kind of administrative responsibilities, role models can inspire all members of the organization and demonstrate that higher productivity is possible despite constraints. As per Theory A, an organization can showcase the performance of role models to improved targets and hence employee performance [12].

(7) Monitoring & Guiding : The next component of Theory A is continuous monitoring of the employees performance and accelerating the productivity of the organization. Such stage will automatically create responsibility and avoid redundancy. Monitoring process in theory A includes both self-monitoring and monitoring by superiors. Continuous monitoring and guiding process provides confidence among the employees and will keep the team together [13].

(8) Accountability : According to Theory A, accountability should be fixed to every member of the organization including the heads of the departments so that satisfaction and justice among the employees can be maintained in the organization. The final component of this organizational performance model is consistency in performance by the individuals. The accountability may be either positive or negative depending on organizational policy for achievers or losers respectively.

Theory of Accountability for HEI :

Table 3 : Perspective of Theory A for Faculty members of HEIs

S. No.	Stages of Theory A	Faculty Members Point of view
1	Planning	To be a research focused faculty
2	Target Setting	Time based research and publication
3	Developing Motivation	Creating habit of research information collection and innovative thinking
4	Devising Work strategies	Collaborative research teams and identifying new research methods & opportunities
5	Creating Responsibility	Struggle to meet the time bound target
6	Identifying Role Model	Role model Researchers enhances confidence of “it is possible” and hence increases commitment
7	Monitoring and Guiding	Performance Evaluation and follow-up
8	Imposing Accountability	Increases performance and effectiveness

5. A proposal of Faculty Compensation Framework based on Theory A :

The salary proposal based on Theory A consists of four components as basic pay at a given grade, as Base pay, Annual increment on base pay, Dearness allowance, and Annual Performance component. This additional annual performance component if considerably high, the faculty members get inspiration and motivation to set their target to contribute to research and publications as per the perspectives given in table 3. This model of variable faculty component stimulates every faculty members and hence every faculty member will get opportunity to earn as much as he can by active involvement in research and publications.

$$S(t) = [B(t)] + [D(B(t))] + [P(t)] \quad \text{----- (1)}$$

Where $B(t) = [B_{(t-1)}(t) + I] \quad \text{----- (2)}$

$$P(t) = [100 \alpha] \quad \text{----- (3)}$$

Where S(t) = total salary in a given grade in a given year t.

B(t) = Base scale in a given year t

D = Annual Dearness Allowance in percentage (%)

I = Annual increment = $x/0$ depending on required publications claimed by one faculty only

n = total year of experience in a given cadre/grade after joining the university

P(t) = Performance Component

α = Annual Performance score calculated using API policy

Table 4 : Autonomous University Pay Structure Proposal

S. No	Grade	Qualification	Experience & Journal Papers	Min Basic Scale & Annual Increment
1	Research Scholars (8 periods/week teaching assistantship)	Full Time Master Degree in Respective subject with 60 % marks & NET/SLET	-	8,000/9,000/10,000 in the first/second / third year
2	Assistant Lecturer (18 periods/week teaching) Rs. 800/year	Full Time Master Degree in Respective subject with 60%	-	18,000 with Rs. 800/year
3a	Lecturer Rs. 1,000/year	Full Time Master Degree in Respective subject with 60% & NET/SLET/M.Phil	2 Years	22,000 with Rs. 1,000/year
3b	Lecturer (Tech) Rs. 1,000/year	M.Tech. with Min. 60%	-	24,000 with Rs. 1,000/year
4a	Sr. Lecturer Rs. 1,200/year	Full Time Master Degree in Respective subject with 60% & NET/SLET/M.Phil.	5 Years (Registered for Ph.D. & 1 paper/year)	27,000 with Rs. 1,200/year
4b	Sr. Lecturer (Tech) Rs. 1,200/year	M.Tech. with Min. 60% in respective subject	5 years (Registered for Ph.D. & 1 paper/year)	29,000 with Rs. 1,200/year
5	Assistant Professor (Institutional-Level 1) Rs. 1,500	Full Time Master's Degree in Respective subject with 60% & NET/SLET/M.Phil.	10 Years ((Registered for Ph.D. & 2 papers/ year)	35,000 with Rs. 1,500/year
6	Assistant Professor (Institutional-Level 2) Rs. 1,600	Full Time Master's Degree in Respective subject with 60% & NET/SLET/M.Phil.	15 Years ((Registered for Ph.D. & 2 papers/ year)	43,000 with Rs. 1,600/year
7	Associate Professor (Institutional) Rs. 1,800	Full Time Master Degree in Respective subject with 60% & NET/SLET/M.Phil.	20 Years ((Registered for Ph.D. & 2 papers/ year)	51,000 with Rs. 1,800/year

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8	Professor (Institutional) Rs. 2,000)	Full Time Master Degree in Respective subject with 60% & NET/SLET/M.Phil.	25 Years ((Registered for Ph.D. & 2 papers/ year)	60,000 with Rs. 2,000/year
9	Assistant Professor (Level 1 UGC) Rs. 2,000	Full Time Master Degree in Respective subject with 60% & Ph.D.	0 Years (5 Journal Paper & 2 papers /year)	50,000 with Rs. 2,000/year
10	Assistant Professor (Level 2 UGC) Rs. 2,000	Full Time Master's Degree in Respective subject with 60%, Ph.D., 3 years experience after Ph.D.	3 years (10 Journal Paper & 2 papers /year)	60,000 with Rs. 2,000/year
11	Assistant Professor (Level 3 UGC) Rs. 2,000	Full Time Master's Degree in Respective subject with 60%, Ph.D., 5 years experience after Ph.D.	5 years (15 Journal Paper & 2 papers /year)	65,000 with Rs. 2,000/year
12	Associate Professor (Level 1 UGC) Rs. 2,300	Full Time Master Degree in Respective subject with 60%, Ph.D., 8 years experience after Ph.D.	8 years (20 Journal Paper & 3 papers /year)	72,000 with Rs. 2,300/year
13	Professor (Level 1) Rs. 2,600	Full Time Master Degree in Respective subject with 60%, Ph.D., 10 years experience after Ph.D.	10 years (25 Journal Paper & 4 papers /year)	80,000 with Rs. 2,600/year
14	Professor (Level 2) Rs. 3,000	Full Time Master Degree in Respective subject with 60%, Ph.D., 20 years experience after Ph.D. (Age ≤ 60)	20 years (30 Journal Paper & 5 papers /year)	1,10,000 with Rs. 3,000/year
15	Senior Professor	Full Time Master Degree in Respective subject with 60%, Ph.D., 30 years experience after Ph.D. (Age ≥ 60)	30 years (50 journal Papers & 6 papers/year)	Institutional fixed salary
16	Emeritus Professor	Full Time Master Degree in Respective subject with 60%, Ph.D., 30 years experience after Ph.D. (Age ≥ 65) till 70 years	30 years (70 journal Papers & 6 papers/year)	Institutional fixed salary

Note : (1) Two extra Increments for M.Tech./MPT/MHM

(2) Dean of a College = Rs. 4,000 extra

(3) Co-ordinator of a Course with number of students more than 100 = Rs. 1,000

Scale :

Asst. Lecturer (I) : 18,000 – 800 – 30,000

Lecturer (I) : 22,000 – 1,000 – 36,000

Sr. Lecturer (I) : 27,000 – 1,200 – 39,000

Asst. Professor Level 1 (I) : 35,000 – 1,500 – 42,500

Asst. Professor Level 2 (I) : 43,000 – 1,600 – 59,000

Assoc Professor (I) : 51,000 – 1,800 – 69,000

Professor (I) : 60,000 – 2,000 – 80,000

Asst. Professor Level 1 (U) : 50,000 – 2,000 – 60,000

Asst. Professor Level 2 (U) : 60,000 – 2,000 – 64,000

Asst. Professor Level 3 (U) : 65,000 – 2,000 – 71,000

Assoc Professor (U) : 72,000 – 2,300 – 76,600 – 2,500 – 81,600

Professor (U) : 80,000 – 2,600 – 1,06,000

Senior Professor (U) : 1,10,000 – 3,000 – 1,40,000

Table 5 : Grade equivalence at HEIs at USA and India :

S. No.	U. S. A. Faculty Grade	Indian Faculty Grade
1	Teaching Assistant	Teaching Assistant
2	Instructor	Assistant Lecturer
3	Lecturer	Lecturer
4	Sr. Lecturer	Sr. Lecturer
5	Asst. Professor	Asst. Professor
6	Associate Professor	Associate Professor
7	Professor	Professor
8	Senior Professor	Senior Professor
9	Emeritus Professor	Emeritus Professor
10	Adjunct Faculty	Visiting Faculty
11	Visiting Faculty	Visiting Faculty

API based performance indicators & Compensation as dynamic component of the salary :

API score 1 = Rs. 100/year

API 10 => 1,000 /year => 1,000/12 = Rs. x /month

API 20 => 2,000 /year => 2,000/12 = Rs. x /month

API 50 => 5,000 /year => (5,000/12) /month

API 100 => 10,000 /year => (10,000/12) = Rs. x/month

API 200 => 20,000/year => 20,000/12 = Rs. x/month

API 300 => 30,000/year => 30,000/12 = Rs. x/month

6. CASE EXAMPLES OF FACULTY PERFORMANCE MODEL :

Case I : Pessimistic Estimate

160 Journal Papers (60 from faculty & 100 from Research scholars)

250 Conference Papers (100 faculty & 150 PG students & Research Scholars)

Table 6 : Pessimistic Estimate

Faculty Designation	Number of Faculty	Journal papers	Conference Papers	Average API	Performance pay cost/year
Professors	10	10	20	150 + 160	31,000
Associated Professors	10	10	10	150 + 80	23,000
Assistant Professors	30	30	30	450 + 240	69,000
Lecturers & Senior Lecturers	50	10	40	150 + 320	47,000
Research Scholars & PG Students	50	100	150	-	-
Total	150	160	250	2,400 + 2,000 = 4,400	1,70,000/year or 14,000/Month

Case II : Realistic Estimate

200 Journal Papers (100 from faculty & 100 from Research scholars)

300 Conference Papers (150 faculty & 150 PG students & Research Scholars)

Table 7 : Realistic Estimate

Faculty Designation	Number of Faculty	Journal papers	Conference Papers	Total API	Performance pay cost/year
Professors	10	20	20	300 + 160	46,000
Associated Professors	10	20	20	300 + 160	46,000
Assistant Professors	30	60	60	900 + 480	69,000
Lecturers & Senior Lecturers	50	50	50	750 + 400	47,000
Research Scholars & PG Students	50	100	150	1,500 + 1,200	-
Total	150	250	400	4,250 + 2,160 = 6,410	1,70,000/year or 14,000/Month

Case III : Optimistic Estimate

500 Journal Papers (300 from faculty & 200 from Research scholars)

500 Conference Papers (300 faculty & 200 PG students & Research Scholars)

Table 8 : Optimistic Estimate

Faculty Designation	Number of Faculty	Journal papers	Conference Papers	Average API	Performance pay cost/year
Professors	10	40	40	150 + 160	31,000
Associated Professors	10	40	40	150 + 80	23,000
Assistant Professors	30	120	120	1,800 + 960	2,76,000
Lecturers & Senior Lecturers	50	100	100	1500 + 800	2,30,000
Research Scholars & PG Students	50 +	200	200	-	-
Total	150+	500	500	7,500 + 4,000 = 11,500	1,70,000/year or 14,000/Month

7. CONCLUSION :

The model of variable faculty component distributed in monthly salary stimulates every faculty members and hence every faculty member will get opportunity to earn as much as he can by active involvement in research and publications. This in turn increases the intellectual property (IP-1) of the HEIs. Thus considering and implementing the option of annual performance based component in the faculty pay, HEIs can increase their contributions to the research and publication and rename themselves as higher education research institution.

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